

The Modern Shatterbelts: Testing the Theory of Borders in Global “Regional System”

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Abstract:

The Shatterbelt Theory is deeply embedded in classical and contemporary geopolitical thought (Fairgrieve, 1917; Whittlesey, 1942; Hartshorne, 1944; Cohen 1963; Huntington, 1997). When labelling regions and explaining world order(s) contacting areas have always been thoroughly challenged. Both from the perspective of defining and belonging as well as from the aspect of power-politics. The aim of this paper is two-folded. First part is oriented towards an overview of shatterbelt theory through development of contemporary border theory while the second part applies two combined theories onto contemporary geopolitical order showing old/new territorial discrepancies and cutting edges. The focus is on macro geopolitical level, but national, and micro levels will be taken into consideration as well. The presumption is that old division lines still exist while new fractures emerge each day. The Shatterbelt Theory is both time and space susceptible but, in some cases, geographical givens are hard to avoid. This paper highlights abovementioned discrepancies and constants. There are few challenges related to Eurocentric, and later so-called western worldview. As it constructed world maps and named world order(s) it has left huge impact on shatterbelts regions on one hand and made its own definition ambiguous on the other. These open-end definitions leave border zones in the constant flux and dependent on current distribution of world power. All mentioned categories are highly subjective making geopolitical analysis the main tool for such categorization and research. Therefore, methodological concept of this paper is embedded in geopolitical analysis of current world power distribution including four key factors – geographical power, social power, economy power and military power – aiming towards redefinition of world regional system, potential shatterbelts and contemporary frontiers. We argue that the concept of frontiers (wide border zones prior to the phase of forming nation states) are being reintroduced in the form of shatterbelts and should be used to define such areas instead of regions. Modern shatterbelts are simultaneously places of hybrid warfare and forgotten no man’s lands. Place of hybrid warfare in a sense of neighboring powers playground and no man’s land in a sense of definition and belonging.

Key words:

Geopolitics, Shatterbelts, Borders, World Regional System, Political Cartography

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Introduction

The innovation of this approach is in its emphasis on borders and border theory in shattered spaces. The ambiguity of shatterbelts and crush zones worldwide relies upon definition of where such contested regions begin and where they end. Border theory and the significance of borders in the context of shatterbelts should highlight how borders shape and influence the dynamics of conflict, competition, and fragmentation within these regions. Borders act as physical and symbolic markers of identity, territory, and control, and understanding their role is crucial for comprehending the complexities of geopolitical processes within shatterbelts. On the other hand, contested regions are hard to define in strict geographical sense, they are geopolitically fluid, and identification of their specific borders is an impossible task. Moreover, such regions have been labeled without respect towards its heterogeneity and/or any kind of regional ownership of the process whatsoever. Identification of crush points leading towards layered zones of various intensity of contestation, rather than regions, may help in understanding shattered spaces both in theory and practice. Starting from the assumption that such spaces are not homogeneous regions with clearly defined borders, but rather multilayered areas of geopolitical conflicts of interest, considering them within the framework of frontiers is helpful for understanding its dynamics and could lead towards more clearly geographical understanding of their spreading.

Labelling spaces and giving them etiquettes of meaning is in the core of classical geopolitics global view since Mackinder's Heartland theory (1904). While such an approach helps in understanding the global world order of given time it simultaneously produces three-fold discrepancies (O Tuathail, Dalby and Routledge, 2007). The first one is related to the presumption that such big world regions are homogenous. From Mackinder's Heartland to Huntington's civilizations, geopolitical labelling creates falsely consolidated spaces with imposed meanings. The second shortage is related to labelling theory in general with labels and etiquettes that impose or subtract power from places. Finally, the third problem is related to labelling usually leading towards opposed world regional system with conflicted characteristics. Moreover, when labelling regions and explaining world order(s), contacting areas have always been thoroughly challenged. Both from the perspective of defining and belonging as well as from the aspect of power-politics. Such in-between spaces were named shatter zones or shatterbelts. And while shatterbelt theory recognizes conflicting meaning of the world order it also depends on particular time-space relation. Even more, practical reasoning of shattered zones in given time frame vary due to the subjectivity, perspective, and imaginations of the author. Because of the ambiguity of such places and its bordering nature it is necessary to test concepts of border studies and border theory in general for understanding of such regional systems.

The major quantity of papers mentioning shatterbelts do not emphasize the borders as key factor in analysis (Fairgrieve, 1917; Whittlesey, 1942; Hartshorne, 1944;

Cohen 1963; Huntington, 1997). On the contrary, it is mostly stated that borders of such regions are being fluid. One must ask oneself how it is possible for borders to be fluid in contested spaces, and if so, what are the actual fragile lines of opposition? Having that in mind we argue that whole shatterbelts are border zones rather than regions and as such might be fluid due to the power play in contesting centers. Therefore, it is essential to apply border theory when analyzing such spaces, emphasizing the reintroduction of frontiers for shattered spaces: zones rather than regions. The second challenge of existing shatterbelt theory is the unit of analysis. Some authors mention clusters of fragile states (Mahan, 1890; Fairgrieve, 1917), some authors refer to fragile regions in general (Cohen, 1963; Ó Tuathail, 1997; Huntington, 1996; Flint, 2004; Murphy & O'Loughlin, 2009; Dodds, 2017). The question here are levels taken into consideration – or if you want – the interchangeable nature of fragile lines that consist of micro spaces, national states and peripheries of global play. Rather than quantifying and calculating fragility of the states in shattered region for making it fit the definition, the complexity of shatter spaces should start from global view (current world order and its fraud lines), the role of states along those lines in question, and micro hotspots along the way. Borders, both physical and symbolic, are central to the functioning of shatterbelts and the dynamics described by the theory.

Borders often define the spatial extent of different ethnic, linguistic, or religious groups within a shatterbelt. The presence of diverse identities and ethnic groups within close proximity can lead to tensions and conflicts over resources, political representation, or cultural dominance. Borders can act as markers of identity and serve as catalysts for identity-based conflicts. Other than Identity and ethnicity-based reasons, borders act as dividing lines. These lines of separation can be highly contentious, as different groups may have competing claims over the same territory. Conflicting territorial claims and border disputes can contribute to the overall instability in shatterbelts. Furthermore, the aspect of security and control is driven through the control of borders and borderlines. Borders are critical for states and actors within shatterbelts to assert control over their territories. They act as a mean to regulate the movement of people, goods, and ideas across political boundaries. Disputes over border control, such as border security, smuggling, or migration, can intensify existing conflicts and contribute to the overall instability in shatterbelts. Border theory in this context is also important since shattered spaces often attract the attention of external powers seeking to exert influence or control over the region. Borders become contested spaces where geopolitical competition takes place. External powers may support different factions within the shatterbelt, leading to proxy conflicts and power struggles along the borders. Finally, in its core definition shatterbelts are characterized by political, social, and ideological fragmentation. Borders within these regions can further contribute to the fragmentation, as different groups may strive for autonomy or independence based on ethnic, cultural, or political differences. This fragmentation can lead to the creation of new borders or the redrawing of existing ones, further complicating the geopolitical landscape.

But, in all those cases one fact remains unclear: What is the nature of borders of shattered spaces? Are they fluid or hard? If they are fluid what changes their nature, and how is it possible that ambiguous space is contested? From the other perspective, if they are hard, solid and defined, why and how are those areas being challenged?

This paper suggests three answers to these questions. The first one is breaking through state subjectivity and contribution of the concept of fragile states to shatterbelt theory. The second one is connected to the nature of borders in shattered spaces. Those borders can be fluid, influenced by contestation, evolving geopolitical dynamics, and changing alliances. While some borders may start out as hard and defined, the contested nature of these spaces can lead to challenges and attempts to redefine or undermine existing borders. Finally, the third one is related to layered circles of power and center-periphery relations perspective in shatterbelt spaces.

The aim of this paper is two-folded. First part is oriented towards an overview of shatterbelt theory and development of contemporary borders and border theory while the second part applies two combined theories onto contemporary geopolitical order showing old/new territorial discrepancies and cutting edges. The focus is on macro geopolitical level, but national, and micro levels will be taken into consideration as well. The presumption is that old division lines still exist while new fractures emerge each day. All mentioned categories are subjective, making qualitative geopolitical analysis the main tool for such categorization and research. Therefore, methodological concept of this paper is embedded in geopolitical analysis of current world power distribution including four key factors – geographical power, social power, economy power and military power – aiming towards redefinition of world regional system, potential shatterbelts and contemporary frontiers.

This paper will provide a state-of-the-art overview of shatterbelt theory from the angle of borders and border realities included. In the second part border theory will be introduced and tested on already defined shatterbelt regions while third part will test findings in practical surrounding of contemporary crush zones and geopolitical flashing points. We argue that the concept of frontiers (wide border zones prior to the phase of forming nation states) are being reintroduced in the form of shatterbelts. Modern shatterbelts are simultaneously places of hybrid warfare and forgotten no man's lands. Place of hybrid warfare in a sense of neighboring powers playground and no man's land in a sense of definition and belonging. Thus, shatterbelts are modern frontiers and border zones and should be analyzed through the complexity of contemporary world system theory marking it contested spaces in a form of modern frontiers.

State of the Art – Shatterbelt Theory with a critical twist?

Classical geopolitical thought theory and their authors highlight constant fight between land and sea powers. Their contact points are defined as contested

nonetheless the name given to such spaces – from crush zones, shatter zones, shatterbelts or geopolitical flashpoints. Starting with Mackinder, the key to ruling the world was Eastern Europe – contested point of contact between Heartland and Rimland (land and sea powers) (Mackinder, 1904). Although Mackinder does not define Eastern Europe as a shatterbelt it is evident that he gives the upmost importance to this geographical region, naming it the key for ruling the World. Mackinder believed that the Heartland, with its vast resources, strategic location, and relative inaccessibility, held the key to global power. He saw Eastern Europe as a crucial region due to its geographical position at the heart of the Eurasian landmass. In his view, whoever controlled this region could potentially control the entire “World-Island”, a term he used to describe the interconnected landmass of Europe, Asia, and Africa. Mackinder argued that the Heartland's central location, abundant resources (such as coal and iron), and the potential to mobilize a large population gave it an inherent advantage. He argued that control over this region would provide the ability to project power outward and control the surrounding “Rimland” regions, which included Western Europe, East Asia, and the coastal areas of Eurasia. In essence, Mackinder saw Eastern Europe as a key to world domination because he believed that controlling this region would grant a nation immense geopolitical power. By dominating the Heartland, a state could potentially control the vast resources, transportation routes, and influence over neighboring regions, thus establishing a position of global supremacy. But starting with this theory one must recognize that Eastern Europe is a vague term, at least when it comes to its borders in specific time period, orientation and scope.

It's worth noting that Mackinder's Heartland Theory has been subject to various criticisms and debates among scholars, and the world has undergone significant geopolitical changes since he first proposed his ideas in the early 20th century. However, his theories continue to be influential in the field of geopolitics and have contributed to discussions on the strategic significance of certain regions in global affairs. Moreover, it makes him the first author that contributed to the theory of shatterbelt spaces in general setting the ground for labelling world regions and contested spaces between them. Like Mackinder, Hartshorne, naming it Shatter zones, defines Eastern and Southeastern Europe as a crucial region(s) for world stability. Calling upon creating World organization(s) in order to provide security and stability he implies that “stability in the shatter zone cannot be achieved by absorption from the outside, ... nor by the reestablishment of free but hopelessly small units, but only by integration into a free association of free peoples, capable of providing a major element of its own defense” (Hartshorne, 1944: 214).” Moreover, “The problem of security as the requirements of modern economy demand a more effective organization of large blocks in this part of Europe, blocks large enough to impose some considerable obstacle, checking any potential new effort of German expansion” (Hartshorne, 1944: 212). Writing in a particular historical moment, he sought for mechanisms of providing world peace and found one in uniting capabilities of Europe.

Furthermore, Whittlesley (1942) divided the world into distinct regions based on both physical and cultural characteristics. His classification system aimed to capture the diversity and uniqueness of different areas across the globe. Although not mentioning the concept of shatterbelts at first, he defines the zone of Eastern Europe challenging as well. His follower Saul Cohen (1963, 2015) has made important contributions to the understanding of shatterbelts and gateways. In his new geopolitical division of the world, the spaces that do not belong to either of the two major powers are called “Gateways” and “Shatterbelts”. Regarding shatterbelts, Cohen describes them as regions characterized by their fragmentation, instability, and propensity for conflict due to their location between powerful and competing geopolitical forces. These areas often experience internal divisions, ethnic or religious tensions, and are subject to the influence of external actors vying for control. Shatterbelts are seen as zones of geopolitical contestation and are crucial in the analysis of global power dynamics. As for gateways, Cohen refers to them as strategic locations that hold significant geopolitical and economic importance due to their function as transit points or channels of access between regions. Gateways can be natural, such as waterways or mountain passes, or artificial, like major transportation hubs or chokepoints. These areas are essential for the movement of goods, people, and ideas, and they can shape trade routes, alliances, and conflicts. In his analysis the key emphasis is on stability, so war and peace theory in this context should be mentioned as well.

At the beginning of the 21st century, Cohen developed Shatterbelts theory and defines it as: “a region torn by internal conflicts whose fragmentation is increased by the intervention of external major powers” (Cohen; 2015: 9). As he warns, great powers are prone to meddling in political, military, and economic affairs within the states of unstable regions with the aim of providing support to their clients. “Shatterbelts, which form zones of contact between realms, may be divided into separate subplates, such as compression zones, by such movement or totally subsumed within one realm. Regions, or medium-sized plates, may also change their shapes and boundaries as they shift within realms or from one realm to another, becoming convergence zones. Compression zones, or regional subplates, may be formed or disappear with shifting within regional plates” (Cohen, 2015: 40). “Compression zones”—smaller atomized areas that lie within or between geopolitical regions – are torn apart by the combination of civil wars and the interventionist actions of neighboring countries” (Cohen, 2015: 9). Cohen explains that: “Shatterbelts and their boundaries are fluid” (Cohen, 2015: 48). For such a concept peace and war theory with its peace-building and peace-making mechanisms is prone to creation and re-creation of shatterbelts or frontiers of insecurity. So, the key question is how to interpret the insecurity and what are the final limits of border fluidity in a sense of definition of shatterbelt spaces. A contemporary author Phil Kelly also rethinks shatterbelt theory through the concept of security/insecurity. His analysis includes several world regions as contemporary shatterbelts. He identifies “four conceptual problems encountered in traditional descriptions as a means toward improving the term's utility: shatterbelt uniqueness,

dynamism, location, and escalation potential” (Kelly, 1986: 161). As explained, the important parts of this concept include individual case study approach (uniqueness); time specification (dynamism); geographical factor (location) and (in)security (escalation potential). All of the abovementioned categories will be included in our analysis. Furthermore, Kelly suggests a new definition for shatterbelts: “a shatterbelt is a geographic region over whose control great powers seriously compete. Great powers compete because they perceive strong interests for doing so and because opportunities are present for establishing alliance footholds with states of the region. Consequently, a high potential exists for escalation of conflict into major power warfare. A shatterbelt originates when rival great powers have footholds in a single area. Six contemporary world regions met the criteria of this standard: the Middle East, East Asia, Southeast Asia, Sub-Saharan Africa, Middle America, and South Asia”. (Kelly, 1986: 161) Closer to our proposition of modern frontiers, Kelly recognizes competitive frame as important one but keeps referring to such spaces in a form of region(s).

Other authors engaged in shatterbelt theory are using the term in similar matter – the one of (in)stability. Biondich (2014) uses the terms for zones of violence in WW1, while Bugge (2002) also engage historical perspective in Eastern Europe geographical area. Similarly, Bartov & Weitz (2013) are doing historical perspective in their study oriented towards European empires and their peripheries. From this perspectives, center-periphery theory seems relevant for development of shatterbelt concept in this particular timeframe. Antun Gosar (2000: 107) test this centre-periphery idea on Slovenia stating that: “Europe in general is in a great state of change. States uniting with difficulty, states collapsing in pain, newly freed states struggling for new political, economic, and social identities - it is a region in a true transition”. He is focused on, as he calls it, “European Shatter Belt, formerly known as ‘Eastern Europe’”. And yes, most of the authors dealing with crush zones, zones of instability and shatterbelts name eastern part of Europe as a fragile one although does not really explain what Eastern Europe means in geographical sense. Same region is in the focus of later Saul Cohen’s (2005) work where he studies geopolitical implications of U.S. influence in a vast Eurasian Convergence Zone, within which the influence of major world geopolitical powers (Maritime Europe, Russia, China, India, and Japan) intersects. After a comprehensive analysis of the U.S. involvement in key segments of the Zone (specifically Eastern Europe, Transcaucasus, Central Asia, and East Asia), Cohen proceeds to explore the economic, demographic, and military strategic interests of major geopolitical actors in this region. Eastern Europe is not uncommonly defined as a shatterbelt. George W. Hoffman (1972: 265) even uses singular to apostrophe its importance. He defines the Shatterbelt as: “between the Soviet Union and what is generally called Western Europe bordered by four seas – Baltic, Adriatic, Aegean and Black seas – is located an area which in many ways occupies a central position in Euroasia. Various names are given to this area – East Central Europe, Eastern Europe, Central Europe, Middle Europe – but geographers for some times have been calling this region “The Shatter-Belt””. Closest to defining

the region in geographical sense he still identifies that space in regional sense giving it homogenous meaning and calling upon non-existing regional characteristics.

Other than by attempts in defining geographical location shatterbelts are being defined by conflict potential. David Reilly (2000: 48) divides states on those with high-risk and low-risk conflict behavior bearing in mind shatterbelt areas and globalization processes. By examining how conflict behavior has changed over time, and in conjunction with trade openness, his results indicate that “domestic instability and fragmentation are more directly tied to high-risk state behavior than are systemic influences. In contrast, the probability that low-risk states originate or participate in conflicts, and resort to violence, is tied to international factors”. His findings suggest that “trade openness has an important pacifying effect on high-risk states, but appears to be irrelevant to the conflict behavior of all others”(Ibidem).

Phil Kelly suggests that “most 20th-century wars among major powers have originated in shatterbelts, geographic regions from which local turmoil escalates to serious competition among outside larger states. Because of the concept's impredness, the relevance of shatterbelts to war and peace largely has been ignored within international affairs literature” (Kelly, 1986: 161). Two other authors, Paul R. Hensel and Paul F. Diehl, tested the theory of shatterbelts and their conflict potential in empirical rather than as they call it “impressionistic” manner. Their findings are similar to qualitative contributions as: “the results indicate that shatterbelts are more likely than other regions to be the setting for interstate wars, but this is largely because they also generate more militarized disputes that can go to war, rather than because of any greater likelihood that those lesser conflicts will escalate. Internal conflicts were also more common in shatterbelts, although the effect was more modest than with interstate conflict. The portion of conflicts, especially interstate wars, that involve outside intervention is greater in shatterbelts. Yet, given that intervention occurs, conflicts in shatterbelts (with the exception of interstate wars) are not more likely to expand further or to include major powers as the intervening parties. Shatterbelt conflicts, both internal and external, were also generally considerably longer and bloodier than conflicts in other regions” (Hensel and Diehl, 1994: 33).

But, regarding contemporary space/place relations one must ask themselves is it even possible to rethink shatterbelt theory through solely territorial lenses and how could cyberspace be included. The emphasis on competition between sea and land powers seems a bit outdated in an era of virtual interconnections and contestations. How is it possible for territorial flash points to remain as important as ever? There are two possible explanations. The first one is related to the thesis of learned behavior. So, power games and territorial contestations mirrored to outer space and cyber space as well. Although they lack a territorial component, these spaces also become arenas of power struggle, where states and other subjects of international relations engage in familiar principles of competition and rivalry. While shatterbelts originally referred to geopolitical regions characterized by multiple conflicting interests and contested boundaries, the concept can be applied to other domains,

including the cyber realm. In the cyber context, a shatterbelt can be understood as an area or zone where different actors with diverse interests and agendas engage in intense competition, conflict, or power struggles. These conflicts may involve issues such as data sovereignty, cybersecurity, information warfare, or control over critical infrastructure. Shatterbelts in cyberspace can emerge due to a variety of factors. These may include geopolitical rivalries, economic interests, ideological differences, or attempts to exert influence and control over digital networks and resources. As various actors with different goals and capabilities operate within the cyber domain, they may vie for control, seek to shape norms and standards, or engage in offensive and defensive cyber operations. Similar to traditional shatterbelts, cyber shatterbelts exhibit fluid boundaries and contested spaces. The nature of cyberspace allows for rapid and dynamic shifts in power and influence, as actors adapt their strategies and tactics in response to changing circumstances. Shatterbelts in the cyber domain can also be characterized by ambiguity, as the attribution of cyber-attacks and the determination of responsibility can be challenging. Furthermore, the interconnected nature of cyberspace means that conflicts and power struggles within one defined or named shatterbelt can have ripple effects across other regions or even globally. Cybersecurity incidents, such as large-scale data breaches or disruptive cyber-attacks, can impact multiple actors and regions, leading to broader destabilization and tensions and goes beyond regional contexts.

Visualization of data in political cartography and limitations of the research

Critical twist refers both to new subjectivity and new spaces of struggle while engaging the same classical mechanisms of geopolitical power games in contemporary environment. Therefore, there are several restrictions in visualization of potential world orders and world power distribution. Cartography and visualization are inherently subjective and can be influenced by the biases and perspectives of the mapmakers or data analysts. Representing power distribution requires making choices about what factors to include, how to classify or categorize data, and what symbols or colors to use, which can introduce unintentional or intentional biases.

Moreover, power dynamics in the world are constantly evolving, with shifts in economic, political, and military influence among countries and regions. Keeping up with these changes and accurately reflecting the current distribution of power can be challenging, especially as emerging powers gain prominence and traditional power structures undergo transformations. Therefore time-space continuum should be taken into consideration as well. Additionally, reliable and up-to-date data on power distribution can be difficult to obtain, especially in countries with limited transparency or political complexities. Data collection methods, access to information, and the quality of data sources can vary across regions, making it challenging to ensure accuracy and consistency in power visualizations. Finally, power distribution is not solely based on a single indicator or factor but is influenced

by multiple interrelated variables, including economic strength, military capabilities, technological advancements, diplomatic influence, cultural influence, and more.

Shihai Wu and Jianzhong Yan (2022: 1109) suggest future elements for shatterbelt research in China (as a new emerging power). Their ideas include: “1) constructing a theoretical analysis framework of shatter belt, and strengthening the visualization, quantification, and simulation of shatter belt by combining big data and other analytical methods; 2) strengthening the examination of the evolution processes and driving mechanisms of shatter belts in China's peripheral regions and along the Belt and Road, and identifying and assessing the geopolitical risks in shatter belts; and 3) exploring the ways to integrate shatter belts by combining the thought of a community with shared future for mankind”. Strongly agreeing with the first one the model and map of current shaterbelt areas will be analyzed in following chapter.

If new subjectivity (other than states) is included as well as new areas of battle (or contested spaces e.g. cyberspace) there are practical challenges in visualization of potential contemporary shatterbelts and fraud lines. For example, when John B. Sparks tried to create visual representation of the history of world power, his Histomap had no geographical data whatsoever.

Picture 1: Histomap and its perspectives.³

³ Source: Sparks, John B. (1931) The Histomap. Four Thousand Year of World History. Relative Power of Contemporary States, Nations, and Empires. Chicago: Histomap Inc., Cartography Associates, David Rumsey Collection, available on Visual Capitalist, <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/histomap-big.html>, 7/7/2023.

Other than time continuum, visualization of new subjects other than states is challenging using classical cartography methods. Kaplan (1996) suggest hologram of mobile axes of power as one of possible solutions in such contested spaces (in his case Africa). Moreover, new spaces of contestation, from outer Space to cyber are impossible to visualize in 2D cartographical solutions. Holographic visualization refers to a three-dimensional representation of data or information using holographic technology. In the context of world order or power, holographic visualization can be applied to depict the distribution and dynamics of global power relations in a spatial and interactive manner.

One of the solutions for power related visualizations are power-relations maps. This kind of maps do not follow geographical realities but introduce relations as a key factor for visualization. These kinds of cartograms show more accurately and in real time relations rather than geographically correct data and facts. Power-related maps and diagrams are useful tools for presenting complex information, enhancing understanding, supporting decision-making, and fostering discussions about global power dynamics. They provide valuable insights into the distribution, dynamics, and implications of power, contributing to a deeper understanding of geopolitics and international relations. Power-related maps and diagrams help simplify and visualize complex data related to power distribution, such as geopolitical influence, economic strength, military capabilities, or diplomatic relationships.

Picture 2 – Raffestin’s Power-relation map.⁴

⁴ Source: Raffestin, Claude; Lopreno, Dario; Pasteur, Yvan (1995). Géopolitique et Histoire. Paris: Payot.

By presenting information in a visual format, these visualizations make it easier to grasp and understand patterns, trends, and relationships. They can present spatial relationships, highlight regional disparities, or demonstrate the concentration or diffusion of power across different areas. Power-related maps and diagrams often generate discussion, debate, and further exploration of global power dynamics. They serve as a catalyst for critical thinking, academic research, and policy discourse. By visualizing power distribution, these visualizations can stimulate conversations about equity, geopolitics, international relations, and the distribution of resources and influence. In this context it helps in showing and analyzing contemporary shatterbelt spaces as well.

The conceptualization of used data

Suggested visualizations request data background related to rankings of powers and world power distribution. Hence, the aforementioned enumerations necessitate revision to encompass all four dimensions of geopolitical power: 1) geographical power, encompassing factors such as size, location, and resource endowment; 2) social and political power, encompassing demographic characteristics, ideological influence, and public diplomacy; 3) economic power, reflecting the economic indicators and factors that influence it; and 4) military power. Geographical power is rooted in parameters such as territorial expanse, state positioning, and availability of natural resources. Social and political power incorporates demographic statistics and the political conditions necessary for stability. Visualizations of economic power are contingent upon the data considered and may vary accordingly (Zorko and Cesarec, forthcoming 2024). The WorldAtlas combines different economical parameters and the data because: “golden palaces on public display are not always the full story behind a country's financial worth. Thanks to the digital age, the accuracy of modern economic data can now reveal whether nations are a financial success or a disaster in disguise. To do so, three metrics measure the wealth of a country: First, purchasing power parity (PPP) is a metric used to compare the buying power of different countries' currencies, measured by the price of certain goods in each country. Second, gross domestic product (GDP) is an annual measure of the market value of all the final goods and services produced and sold in a country. 'GDP per capita (PPP)' is therefore found by dividing GDP by the total population after adjusting for PPP. Last, GNI per capita is the gross national income divided by population. After accounting for the relevant 2023 data from the International Monetary Fund, these Richest Countries in the World stand out amongst their peers.” (www.worldatlas.com, 3/27/23)

The final aspect, military power, should also be approached with a multi-dimensional perspective. By combining various indicators related to firepower, army strength, and military capabilities, a more comprehensive understanding of this facet of state power can be obtained. Military power, while intricately linked to economic, technical, and industrial capabilities, holds a distinct position as an indicator in geopolitical analysis. For instance, Josip Lučev (2014) introduced the Current

Capacity Indicator (CCI) during his analysis of superpowers and their military capacities. CCI proves valuable in comparative assessments of superpowers as it combines indicators of economic and military power, highlighting their potential. In the realm of cyberspace, cyber capabilities have the potential to compensate for deficiencies in other dimensions of state power. The cyberspace represents a novel domain in which even small states can attain power, transcending conventional definitions and classical notions of power associated with geography or social power (Zorko and Cesarec, forthcoming 2024).

Bearing in mind different Indexes of World Power and World Power Distribution, they often include several key indicators such as economic power, military power, political or geopolitical power, geographical factors, and technological advancements. Such visualizations often include assessing and analyzing the relative strength, influence, and capabilities of different actors in the international system. World power distribution refers to the distribution or allocation of power among nations and entities on a global scale. Measured by different authors the scale might change over time as well.

Picture 3 – The visualization of world power distribution over time in the competitiveness⁵

⁵ Source: The Visual Capitalist, <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/cp/competitive-countries-rankings/>, 7/16/2023.

Picture 4 – Economic power and projections for future⁶

It's important to note that power distribution is a dynamic and complex concept that evolves over time. It requires continuous assessment and analysis, considering multiple dimensions and indicators, to understand the changing dynamics of global power structures. States can be divided regarding power scale in various ways, depending on the specific criteria or framework used for analysis. Here are a few common ways in which states are often categorized based on their power scale: superpowers, great powers, regional powers, middle powers and small states. Somewhere in-between these definitions there are Huntington's states that does not fit into its civilizational (regional) framework. "In the post-Cold War world, countries relate to civilizations as member states, core states, lone countries, cleft countries, and torn countries" (Huntington, 1996: 135) Huntington, in the realm of affiliation, explains member and core states as ones belonging to civilizational patterns, lone states as ones that do not belong to either big world civilization and cleft and torn countries as ones that do not belong to its civilizational core. Although there is a lot to be said about Huntington thesis his countries that does not fit its civilizational background generate instability and multiply fraud lines that could be interpreted as shatter zones.

Finally, political cartography may provide fairest solution – by keeping accurate geographical parameters and adding power-relations as well. Political cartography

⁶ . Source: The Visual Capitalist, www.visualcapitalist.com, 7/11/2023.

“is not an illustration that follows and imitates previous or given contents, which is a characteristic of every illustration. In contrast, political cartography precedes conclusions, and the spatial relationships and contents it portrays serve as the basis for relevant political analyses and conclusions” (Pavić, 1984: 103). In the roughest definitions of maps in political cartography by Radovan Pavić (2012: 117) there are “two kinds of maps: first, general geographic maps, which are of a synthesizing nature as they contain as many different contents as possible, aiming to represent the objective and comprehensive reality as fully as possible. And secondly, there are applied maps that portray only specific contents, issues, and ideas, and they can also be of two types: a) analytical when they represent only one content, and then b) synthesizing when they show various specific contents, but not in a simple accumulation manner, rather in the form of interconnectedness and interplay of individual contents gathered around a common idea or problem”. Following these instructions, we are using both analytical and syncretical political cartography approach in our visualization of modern shatterbelts.

The Modern Shatterbelts: Global “Regional System” and its fraud lines

The methodology for our concept is based on political cartography visualization of big data. Combining aforementioned indexes of world power, classifying them into power related state categories and bearing in mind regional specifics driven out of Huntington classification our map present contemporary global regional system and its fraud lines defined as frontiers of interest rather than shatterbelts.

Envisioning the current world power distribution and bearing in mind power-related categories as superpowers, great powers and regional powers we followed Geographics Magazine’s *Guide of International Power* and combined it with Pareto’s *Global Power Index Ranking for 2023* (<https://pareto-economics.com/global-power-index/>, 7/29/2023). We decided to sort superpowers (current, ex and emerging) with great powers, and they are USA, China, Russia, United Kingdom, Germany, France and Japan. Regional powers and regional Pivots are following: Argentina, Australia, Brazil, Egypt, India, Indonesia, Iran, Israel, Italy, Mexico, Nigeria, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, South Korea, South Africa, Turkey and Vietnam. European Union and Global cities are noted as well since new subjects emerge other than states. The ranking list for 2022 in global cities is New York, London, Paris, Tokyo, Beijing (<https://www.kearney.com/industry/public-sector/global-cities/2022>, 7/29/2023). Trough centre-periphery theory author’s sheched spheres of influence accordingly.

Bearing in mind strong interconnections between shatterbelts and places of war and insecurity author’s combined three online sources for mapping world conflicts and illustrated them (<https://www.visualcapitalist.com/mapped-where-are-the-worlds-ongoing-conflicts-today/>, <https://www.thenewhumanitarian.org/maps-and-graphics/2017/04/04/updated-mapped-world-war>, and <https://www.cfr.org/global-conflict-tracker>, 7/29/2023.. They are as follows:

Russo-Ukrainian War, Nagorno Karabakh (Armenia-Azerbaijan) conflict, Turkish internal conflict with Kurds, Israel-Palestine, Wars in Afghanistan and in Syria, instabilities in Iraq and Yemen, Lebanon, Egypt and DR Congo, Libyan and South Sudanese civil wars, US-Iran conflict, India-Pakistan conflict, Tigray war in Ethiopia, Mali war, Boko Haram Militancy in Nigeria, Al-Shabaab in Kenya and Ethiopia, violence in Central African Republic, East and South China Sea disputes and North-South Korea Crisis. Although mentioned sources include Mexico as well authors suggest interpreting this drug-cartel related insurgencies as internal conflict and problems of a weak political system.

Picture 5 – Author's Power Map⁷

⁷ Tool for creation: www.mapchart.net, 7/29/2023

Sources: Global and Regional pivots, Great Powers and Superpowers – Geographics Magazine, Guide of International Power, https://web.facebook.com/geographics2.0/posts/guide-of-international-powers-can-you-tell-whats-difference-between-a-regional-p/300315378213373/?_rdc=1&_rdt, 7/29/2023.

Spheres of Influence (centre-periphery based) – author's visualization

Global cities – Kearney, <https://www.kearney.com/industry/public-sector/global-cities/2022>, 7/29/2023.

Current War Zones. Combination of Sources: The Visual Capitalist, <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/mapped-where-are-the-worlds-ongoing-conflicts-today/>, 7/29/2023; The New Humanitarian, <https://www.thenewhumanitarian.org/maps-and-graphics/2017/04/04/updated-mapped-world-war>,

7/29/2023; The Center for Preventive Action's (CPA) Global Conflict Tracker, <https://www.cfr.org/global-conflict-tracker>, 7/29/2023.

Global Borders of Walled World. Big Think, 2019, <https://bigthink.com/strange-maps/walled-world/>, 7/29/2023.

Macoregional Shatterbelts – Frontiers of Insecurity of Global World System – author's interpretation

Before concluding and defining Macroregional Shatterbelts – Frontieres of Insecurity of Global World System – in author’s interpretation authors included concept of Walled World in its Power Map political cartography analysis. As it is shown in Power map modern shatterbelt is consistent of local fraud lines interconnection in global frontier of insecurity that stretches from Eastern Europe to Eastern Asia including African continent. It would be important for future research to further classify local African shatterbelts and research its origins and potential reaches.

Conclusion

The main division in rethinking the theory of shatterbelts in contemporary relations has at least two perspectives. Classical geopolitical thought is based on regional perspective of big intersecting regions over time and their contact points. Critical geopolitical thought relies on constructivism, geopolitical imaginations and perceptions of belonging rather than geographical givens in particular timeframes. The classical approach to geopolitics emphasizes the importance of states, territories, and geographical factors in shaping international relations. It focuses on the strategic significance of geographical locations, resources, and territorial control. In such constellation shatterbelts are expected outcomes of world regional system in constant contestation. Classical geopolitics assumes that the world is primarily shaped by the struggle for power and control over territory.

The critical approach challenges the traditional state-centric perspective and explores the power dynamics, social constructions, and discourses that shape geopolitics. It examines how geopolitical knowledge is produced, contested, and used by different actors. Therefore, shatterbelts are constructs of imagined outlines in world power struggles and assumed as contested spaces in-between regional powers/actors. Critical geopolitics challenges the deterministic and essentialist assumptions of classical geopolitics. It recognizes that geopolitical narratives and boundaries are socially constructed and contested. Shatterbelts are seen as socially, and politically constructed spaces shaped by competing interests and discourses. Therefore, non-traditional actors (rather than states), and non-traditional spaces (cyberspace) should be taken into consideration as well. Overall, the classical approach to shatterbelts tends to emphasize the physical and strategic aspects of these regions, while the critical approach takes a more nuanced and interdisciplinary view, examining the social, political, and discursive dynamics at play.

Both perspectives share common ground: the definition of world regions and their fraud lines or contested spaces depends on distribution of world power. Therefore, the World System as a whole should be referred to as the unit of analysis. There are two levels of contested spaces that we suggest defining as modern frontieres – ones on the macro level of the world system and ones on the micro level important in local frames. Although even microlevel fraud lines might influence global (in)security, their wellbeing is often linked to internal success and political stability.

Also, such visualizations are time-sensitive so time frame should be included in this kind of research as well. Other than perspectives, the classical and critical geopolitical theory approaches to shatterbelts differ in their assumptions, and analytical frameworks. Analytical Framework of Classical Geopolitical Theory tends to analyze shatterbelts through a state-centric lens, focusing on military strategies, territorial control, and the balance of power between states. It emphasizes geographical factors such as proximity, resources, and transportation routes. The critical approach employs interdisciplinary methods and analyzes shatterbelts through a broader socio-political lens. It examines the social, economic, cultural, and historical dimensions of shatterbelts, including identities, conflicts, power relations, and discourses. Both perspectives were taken into consideration in our analysis.

Moreover, classical geopolitics primarily focuses on the stability, security, and balance of power in shatterbelts. It explores how states and major powers seek to control and influence these regions to enhance their own geopolitical interests. Critical geopolitics focuses on the contestation and power relations within shatterbelts. It examines how different actors, such as states, non-state actors, and social movements, navigate and shape these spaces. Therefore, it is crucial to realize that in both perspectives borders and border theory is relevant and should be taken into consideration when rethinking shatterbelts and shatterbelt theory.

The nature of borders in shattered spaces can vary and is often characterized by fluidity rather than being strictly hard or solid. Additionally, the fluidity of borders in global shattered spaces can be influenced by geopolitical dynamics, power struggles, and changing alliances. As the interests and priorities of different actors evolve, so can the borders and boundaries that demarcate their spheres of influence. Envisioning shatterbelt theory through border studies enriches the concept of border fluidity naming it frontier of insecurity. Such frontier changes and vary accordingly. Other than border theory center-periphery theory should be used for visualization of contemporary contested spaces – current shatterbelts are contested modern frontiers in a frame of power-distribution. Such modern shatterbelts are border zones of power-influence international gameplay. That means that shattered spaces are not geographically doomed, but historically challenged and geopolitically envisioned as spaces of power-play. They are not regions since region envision homogeneity and at least some level of cohesion. Incorporating huge differences between developed and developing world such insecurities multiply accordingly. Author's Power Map based on combination of indexes of world power and using political cartography as a method of data visualization show that current contested space or modern frontier of insecurity cover the vast of developing world along the fraud lines of Walled World (). Although this visualization may remind us on Thomas P.M. Barnett's "The Pentagon's New Map" (2004), authors does not suggest that globalization is or could be the driving force in the case of modern frontiers but distribution of world power.

References:

- Barnett, T.P.M. (2004) *The Pentagon's New Map*. New York: Penguin Books.
- Bartov, O; Weitz, E. D. (eds) (2013) *Shatterzone of Empires: Coexistence and Violence in the German, Habsburg, Russian and Otoman Borderlands*. Bloomington and Indianapolis: Indiana University Press.
- Biondich, M. (2014). Eastern Borderlands and Prospective Shatter Zones: Identity and Conflict in East Central and Southeastern Europe on the Eve of the First World War. In J. Böhler, W. Borodziej & J. Puttkamer (Ed.), *Legacies of Violence: Eastern Europe's First World War* (pp. 25-50). München: De Gruyter Oldenbourg.
- Bugge, P. (2002). 'Shatter Zones': The Creation and Re-creation of Europe's East. In: Spiering, M., Wintle, M. (eds) *Ideas of Europe since 1914*. Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- Cohen S. B. (1963) *Geography and Politics in a World Divided*; New York: Random House.
- Cohen S. B. (2005) The Eurasian Convergence Zone: Gateway or Shatterbelt?, *Eurasian Geography and Economics*, 46(1): 1-22.
- Cohen S. B. (2015) *Geopolitics: The Geography of International Relations*. Lanham/Boulder/New York/London: Rowman & Littlefield.
- Dodds, K. (2017). 'Awkward Antarctic nationalism': Bodies, ice cores and gateways in and beyond Australian Antarctic Territory/East Antarctica. *Polar Record*, 53(1): 16-30.
- Fairgrieve, F. (1917) *Geography and World Power*; New York: E.P.Dutton & Company.
- Flint, C. (ed.) (2004) *The Geography of War and Peace: From Death Camps to Diplomats*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Geographics Magazine, Guide of International Power, https://web.facebook.com/geographics2.0/posts/guide-of-international-powers-can-you-tell-whats-difference-between-a-regional-p/300315378213373/?_rdc=1&_rdr, accessed 7/29/2023.
- Gosar, A. (2000) The Shatter Belt and the European Core - A Geopolitical Discussion on the Unotypical Case of Slovenia. *GeoJournal* 52(2): 107-117.
- Hartshorne, R. (1944) The United States and "Shatter Zone" in Europe; in: Weigert, H. and Stefansson, V., *Compass of the World*; New York: Macmillan.
- Hensel, P. R; Diehl, P. F. (1994) Testing empirical propositions about shatterbelts, 1945-76, *Political Geography*, 13(1): 33-51.
- Hoffman, G. W. (1952) The Shatter-Belt in Relation to the East-West Conflict, *Journal of Geography*, 51(7): 265-275.

-
- Huntington, S. (1993) Sukob civilizacija; in: Ó Tuathail, G.; Dalby, S.; Routledge, P. (eds.) (2007); Uvod u geopolitiku; Zagreb: Politička kultura.
- Huntington, S. (1996) The clash of civilizations and the remaking of world order. New York: SIMON&SCHUSTER.
- Kaplan, R. (1996) Nadolazeća anarhija, in: Ó Tuathail, G.; Dalby, S.; Routledge, P. (eds.) (2007); Uvod u geopolitiku; Zagreb: Politička kultura.
- Kearney, Global Cities Index 2022, <https://www.kearney.com/industry/public-sector/global-cities/2022>, accessed 7/29/2023.
- Kelly, P. L. (1986) Escalation of regional conflict: testing the shatterbelt concept, Political Geography Quarterly, Volume 5, Issue 2, Pages 161-180.
- Mackinder, H. (1904) Gorgrafski stožer povijesti; in: Ó Tuathail, G.; Dalby, S.; Routledge, P. (eds.) (2007) ; Uvod u geopolitiku; Zagreb: Politička kultura.
- Mahan, A. T. (1890) The Influence of Sea Power Upon History 1660-1783; ; Boston: Little Brown and Company.
- Murphy, A; O'Loughlin, J. (2009). New Horizons for Regional Geography. Eurasian Geography and Economics, 50(3): 241-251.
- Ó Tuathail, G; Dalby, S; Routledge, P. (eds.) (2007) Uvod u geopolitiku; Zagreb: Politička kultura.
- Ó Tuathail, G. (1997) At the End of Geopolitics? Reflections on a Plural Problematic at the Century's End. Alternatives: Global, Local, Political, 22(1): 35–55.
- Pareto's Global Power Index Ranking for 2023, <https://pareto-economics.com/global-power-index/>, accessed 7/29/2023.
- Pavić, R. (1984) "Problemi Bliskog i Srednjeg istoka. Aspekti političke kartografije", Politička misao, 21/1-2: 101-114.
- Pavić, R. (2012) "Prilozi primijenjenoj kartografiji", Kartografija i geoinformacije, 11/18: 117-139.
- Raffestin, Claude; Lopreno, Dario; Pasteur, Yvan (1995). Géopolitique et Histoire. Paris: Payot.
- Reilly, D. (2000) Shatterbelts and conflict behaviour: The effect of globalisation on 'high risk' states, Geopolitics, 5(3): 48-77.
- Sparks, John B. (1931) The Histomap. Four Thousand Year of World History. Relative Power of Contemporary States, Nations, and Empires. Chicago: Histomap Inc., Cartography Associates, David Rumsey Collection, available on Visual Capitalist, <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/histomap-big.html>, accessed 7/7/2023.

The Big Think, 2019, <https://bigthink.com/strange-maps/walled-world/>, accessed 7/29/2023.

The Center for Preventive Action's (CPA) Global Conflict Tracker, <https://www.cfr.org/global-conflict-tracker>, accessed 7/29/2023.

The New Humanitarian, <https://www.thenewhumanitarian.org/maps-and-graphics/2017/04/04/updated-mapped-world-war>, accessed 7/29/2023.

The Visual Capitalist, <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/mapped-where-are-the-worlds-ongoing-conflicts-today/>, accessed 7/29/2023;

The World Atlas, www.worldatlas.com, accessed 3/27/23.

Whittlesey, D. (1942) German strategy of world conquest; New York/Toronto: Farrar & Rinehart.

Wu, S; Yan, J. (2022) Progress and prospect of shatter belt research, *Progress in Geography*, 41(6): 1109-1122.

Zorko, M; Cesarec, I. (forthcoming 2024) European Security Space(s): defining and protecting small states cyberspace in Europe, in: Car, V; Mareš, M. (eds.) *Digital Diplomacy and Hybrid Threats – Security Challenges in Contemporary Media Environment*, London: Routledge.